

The Mediating Effect of Resource Allocation Proficiency of School Heads on Institutional Leadership and Teachers' Instructional Engagement

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Abstract. This study investigated how resource allocation proficiency mediated the relationship between institutional leadership and instructional engagement of teachers using structural equation modeling with a non-experimental, descriptive-correlational design. A total of 293 elementary school teachers in Laak South District, Davao de Oro were selected through simple random sampling. Validated and pilot-tested survey instruments ensured the reliability and internal consistency of the data collection. Results showed that institutional leadership of school heads was generally extensive, particularly in learning environment stewardship, although less consistent in student discipline. Instructional engagement of teachers was moderately extensive, with strong emphasis on student engagement but limited integration of technology. Resource allocation proficiency was also moderately extensive, highlighting prioritization of professional development and teaching materials over extracurricular support. Strong positive correlations existed among the three variables, affirming that leadership and resource use are crucial to effective instruction. Path analysis revealed that institutional leadership significantly influenced instructional engagement both directly and indirectly, with resource allocation proficiency acting as a partial mediator. These findings underscored the critical role of both leadership and equitable resource distribution in fostering effective teaching practices.

KEY WORDS

1. Institutional leadership 2. resource allocation proficiency 3. instructional engagement

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1. Introduction

Poor instructional engagement among teachers has emerged as a critical concern in educational settings, adversely affecting both teacher satisfaction and student learning outcomes. This issue is often exacerbated by ineffective leadership and inadequate resource allocation within schools, compelling educators to operate without the necessary tools or support to engage students effectively. Studies, such as those by Jelinska and Paradowski (2021), have shown that without strong institutional leadership and strategic resource management, teachers struggle to maintain high levels of engagement in their classrooms. This situation highlights the need for a deeper understanding of how school heads can enhance instructional engagement through proficient resource allocation. Consequently, this study aims to explore the mediating effect of resource allocation proficiency of school heads on the relationship between

institutional leadership and teachers' instructional engagement, addressing a significant gap in current educational research. Investigating the impact of institutional leadership and resource allocation proficiency of school heads on teachers' instructional engagement in the U.S. reveals several challenges and issues. Berkovich and Hassan (2024) highlighted that principals' digital instructional leadership during the pandemic significantly influenced teachers' intrinsic motivation and students' learning outcomes. However, disparities in access to resources and uneven implementation of digital tools posed barriers to consistent teacher engagement. Similarly, Cox and Mullen (2023) emphasized the challenges faced by principals in Title I rural schools, where limited funding and resource allocation hindered their ability to fully support instructional practices and teacher development. These studies underscore that while strong leadership is critical, its impact on teacher engagement is often constrained by systemic inequities and resource limitations, necessitating a more balanced approach to leadership and resource management to ensure equitable support for teachers. The impact of institutional leadership and resource allocation proficiency on teachers' instructional engagement in Arabian countries is often hindered by systemic and structural issues. The lack of adequate research infrastructure in Saudi Arabia significantly limits educators' performance, reflecting broader challenges in resource allocation across various educational levels (Bhatti et al., 2022). Similarly, while shared decision-making among school leaders and teachers has the potential to enhance instructional engagement, its effectiveness is often undermined by rigid leadership hierarchies and insufficient resource support (Alamri, 2021). These issues point to a gap between leadership practices and the practical needs of teachers. Addressing these challenges requires a strategic focus on equitable resource distribution and adaptive leadership approaches to strengthen teachers' instructional engagement. The relationship between institutional leadership and resource allocation proficiency of school heads with teachers' instructional engagement in Asian countries is influenced by several critical challenges. Transformational leadership has been shown to enhance teacher self-efficacy and student academic performance, but its impact is often hindered by inequitable resource distribution and varying leadership effectiveness within schools (Li Liu, 2022). In rural Thailand, learning-centered leadership faces significant barriers, including inadequate funding and limited professional development opportunities, which directly affect teacher engagement and instructional quality (Kulophas Hallinger, 2021). These issues highlight the importance of aligning leadership practices with resource management to create environments that fully support teachers. Strengthening both leadership capacities and resource allocation strategies is essential to overcoming these contextual limitations and improving instructional engagement. The impact of institutional leadership and resource allocation proficiency on teachers' instructional engagement in the Philippines is shaped by various challenges related to leadership competencies and resource management. Cabigao (2019) highlighted that the professional competencies of school heads significantly influence school outcomes and organizational culture, yet gaps in resource allocation skills often limit their ability to fully support teachers' instructional needs. Similarly, Pana (2023) emphasized that while school heads' instructional leadership is critical for improving teacher performance, the lack of strategic resource allocation hinders the realization of its full potential. These studies underscore that effective leadership must be complemented by resource management proficiency to address teachers' needs and enhance instructional engagement. Addressing these issues requires targeted leadership training programs

that integrate strategic resource allocation to improve both school outcomes and teacher engagement. In the Visayas, the challenges of poor instructional engagement are exacerbated by geographical isolation and cultural diversity. Teachers in rural areas often deal with multilingual classrooms where language barriers present significant obstacles, as noted by Cortes et al. (2022). Also, Boholano et al. (2022) discusses how limited access to technology and educational resources in remote areas hinders teachers' ability to deliver engaging and interactive instruction. These factors necessitate tailored professional development that addresses specific local challenges and promotes inclusive teaching practices that resonate with diverse student populations. Enhancing teacher engagement in these contexts requires targeted interventions that consider the unique educational landscapes of the Visayas. In Laak South District, Davao de Oro, poor instructional engagement among teachers has emerged as a significant concern, adversely affecting educational outcomes and student learning experiences. Various factors contribute to this problem, including inadequate professional development opportunities, which leave teachers ill-equipped to implement contemporary teaching methodologies and curricula effectively. Additionally, insufficient resource allocation often hampers teachers' ability to engage students effectively, as they lack access to essential teaching aids and technology that facilitate modern instructional practices. Moreover, the prevailing institutional leadership styles may not adequately support or motivate teachers, leading to reduced enthusiasm and commitment to teaching. The culmination of these issues not only diminishes the quality of education but also impacts teacher satisfaction and retention, further exacerbating the challenges within the educational ecosystem in the district. The existing body of research, particularly from studies conducted in diverse educational settings such as the U.S. and Arabian countries, highlights a critical gap in understanding how institutional leadership and resource allocation proficiency directly impact teachers' instructional engagement. Notably, Berkovich and Hassan (2024) in the U.S. context, and Bhatti et al. (2022) in Saudi Arabia, indicate that while the theory of effective leadership enhancing teacher motivation and engagement holds, practical implementation often falls short due to resource disparities and systemic limitations. These studies underscore the complex interplay between leadership qualities and resource availability, yet they reveal a gap in applying these insights to systematically improve instructional engagement through enhanced leadership and resource management practices. This gap suggests a need for a nuanced examination of how specifically tailored leadership strategies can overcome contextual barriers to resource allocation and support teacher engagement effectively. In the context of Laak South District, Davao de Oro, there is an urgent need to address this research gap due to the critical challenges faced by the local educational system, as highlighted by the prevalent issues of poor instructional engagement among teachers. The district's struggle with inadequate professional development opportunities and insufficient technological and pedagogical resources mirrors the broader issues identified in international research, yet there is a distinct need for localized strategies that consider the unique socio-economic and cultural dynamics of the region. Conducting a study using a path analysis approach to investigate the influence of institutional leadership and resource allocation proficiency on instructional engagement offers a promising avenue to develop specific interventions tailored to the district's needs. This study is not only timely but essential for developing evidence-based leadership practices that can significantly enhance the educational outcomes in Laak South District, thereby addressing both the immediate needs of the teachers and the

long-term educational goals of the community.

1.1. Theoretical/Conceptual Framework of the Study—This study was Transformational Leadership Theory by Burns (1978). Transformational leadership theory emphasizes how leaders inspire and motivate their followers to achieve higher levels of performance by fostering a vision, providing support, and encouraging innovation. This theory aligns with the study as it highlights the influence of institutional leadership on teachers' instructional engagement by creating a collaborative and inspiring school environment. Transformational leadership serves as a framework for examining how school heads' leadership styles can enhance teacher motivation and resource utilization, ultimately improving instructional practices. It also provides insights into the role of leadership in fostering trust, collaboration, and innovation, which are essential for sustaining high levels of instructional engagement. In addition, the study is supported by Resource-Based View (RBV) Theory by Barney (1991). The Resource-Based View theory posits that an organization's resources, when effectively managed, serve as critical drivers of competitive advantage and performance. This theory is relevant to the study as it explains the role of resource allocation proficiency of school heads in optimizing instructional engagement among teachers. RBV underpins the analysis of how strategic resource management contributes to better teaching outcomes by ensuring that teachers have the tools and support necessary for effective instruction. It also highlights the importance of aligning resources with institutional priorities, ensuring that teachers are equipped to meet the demands of modern educational practices. Lastly, the study build its foundation on Path-Goal Theory by House (1971). Path-Goal theory focuses on how leaders can remove obstacles, provide support, and align team goals with organizational objectives to ensure successful performance. In the context of the study, this

theory explains how school heads guide teachers by allocating resources effectively and providing clear pathways to achieve instructional excellence. It serves as a lens to analyze the direct and mediated impacts of leadership and resource allocation on teachers' engagement. It further helps analyze the effectiveness of leadership strategies in creating supportive environments where instructional goals are clearly defined and achievable. As shown on Figure 1, the study is composed of three variables. The independent variable is institutional leadership of school heads or the competence, skill, and effectiveness demonstrated by educational leaders, such as school heads or administrators, in overseeing and managing the academic aspects of an institution. The measure of institutional leadership of school heads are learning environment stewardship or the deliberate and effective management and enhancement of the educational atmosphere within a school by school heads with a moderate level of proficiency; teacher professional growth or the intentional support and facilitation provided by school heads at a moderate level of proficiency to enhance the continuous development and learning of educators; educational planning competence or the school heads' capability to strategically design, implement, and oversee comprehensive plans for educational improvement and development; and student discipline or the school heads' ability to establish and maintain a conducive and orderly learning environment by implementing effective disciplinary policies and practices. The dependent variable was instructional engagement of teachers or the active involvement and commitment of teachers in the teaching process, characterized by enthusiastic, effective teaching strategies that foster an interactive and inclusive classroom environment. The measure of instructional engagement of teachers are cultivation of critical thinking or the designing and facilitating learning experiences that encourage students to question, analyze, and evaluate information crit-

Fig. 1. Theoretical/Conceptual Framework

ically; promotion of students' engagement or the approach that involves educators intentionally fostering an environment where students actively participate in the learning process; active classroom engagement or the deliberate efforts by educators with a moderate level of commitment to create an environment where students are actively involved and participatory in the learning process; and integration of technology or the intentional use of digital tools and resources by educators with a moderate level of commitment to enhance teaching practices and student learning.

2. Methodology

This section provides a comprehensive overview of the research design, including details on the research respondents, ethical considerations, research instruments, and procedural steps. It also outlines the methods for data collection and analysis, ensuring a clear framework for the study.

2.1. Research Design—In the context of this study, the researcher has opted for a quantitative descriptive-correlational research design. Quantitative research design involves the systematic empirical investigation of observable phenomena via statistical, mathematical, or computational techniques. It focuses on quantifying relationships between variables and often uses surveys or experiments to gather data that can be converted into numbers (Watson, 2015). For this study, utilizing a quantitative research design is highly appropriate. This design will allow for precise measurement of the key variables such as leadership, resource allocation, and instructional engagement and their interrelationships. The ability to quantify these relationships is crucial for testing hypotheses and validating the theoretical framework posited by the research. Moreover, the descriptive research approach is used to observe, describe, and document aspects of a situation as it naturally occurs without manipulating the environment or the participants. It often involves collecting detailed information through surveys, observations, or case studies (Rahi, 2017). In the context of the study on institutional leadership and resource allocation, a descriptive approach would help outline the current state of these variables within schools. It provides a foundational understanding of how school heads manage resources and lead, setting a stage for deeper analysis. Moreover, descriptive statistics derived from survey data could illuminate typical patterns or deviations in leadership behavior and resource management practices. Further, correlational research approach examines the relationship between two or more variables to determine the strength and direction of associations without inferring causality. This method statistically tests whether and how variables are related (Lau, 2017). Utilizing a correlational approach would be suitable for exploring the extent to which institutional leadership and resource allocation proficiency relate to instructional en-

agement among teachers. By identifying the strength of these relationships, the study could assess significant predictors of engagement outcomes. Furthermore, this approach helps in establishing whether the relationships are positive or negative, providing insights crucial for leadership development strategies. Furthermore, path analysis is a specialized type of statistical technique in structural equation modeling that examines direct and indirect relationships among variables within a theoretical model. It allows for the simultaneous modeling of multiple relationships to disentangle the effects of various predictors on outcome variables (Land, 1969). Applying path analysis in this study is particularly apt as it would enable researchers to decipher the direct influences of institutional leadership and resource allocation proficiency on teachers' engagement, as well as any mediating effects of other variables like school climate or teacher satisfaction. This analysis can provide a comprehensive view of how multiple factors interconnect and impact the main outcome. Additionally, path analysis helps in testing the theoretical framework of the study, making it a powerful tool for understanding complex processes in educational settings.

2.2. Ethical Consideration—The researcher strictly followed the established protocols outlined in the standard guidelines for executing the research, paying close attention to the specified criteria for managing both the population and the data. The survey questionnaires along with other related materials were submitted for evaluation and approval. Upon receiving the green light from the RMC-Ethics Committee, the researcher proceeded to the subsequent phase of the study.

2.3. Research Respondents—In this study, the targeted respondents are the 293 elementary school teachers located in the Laak South District of Davao de Oro. The selection of this specific number of teachers from a total of 1096 teaching staff in the district is determined using

Slovin's formula, which calculates an optimal sample size based on the total population and a desired margin of error. For this calculation, with a population of 1096 and a margin of error set at 5%, to ensure a representative sample, the study utilized a simple random sampling method. This probabilistic approach gave each teacher in the district an equal opportunity to be selected, which helps to eliminate selection bias and promotes fairness in the sampling process (Boschetti, Stehman Roy, 2016). Each teacher will be assigned a unique identifier, and a random number generator will be used to select 293 individuals. This method helped ensure that the sample reflects a wide cross-section of the district's demographics, thereby supporting the study's credibility and the generalizability of its findings. In this study, the inclusion criteria for selecting respondents focused on elementary school teachers in the Laak South District of Davao de Oro who are currently employed full-time and have been teaching for at least one academic year. This experience threshold ensured that teachers have adequate familiarity with school governance practices and are able to provide informed perspectives on the institutional leadership of their school heads and its impact on their instructional engagement. Teachers must be directly involved in classroom instruction, as this is essential to assess the relevance of governance factors on their engagement levels accurately. By applying these criteria, the study aimed to capture a representative sample of teachers whose insights are integral to understanding the influence of institutional leadership within the district.

2.4. Research Instrument—In the study, the researcher employed questionnaires adapted

2.5. Data Gathering Procedure—Permission to Conduct the Study. The initial step in securing permission to conduct the study involved the researcher obtaining an endorsement from

from various studies, modified to align with the specific context of the respondents. The instrument was divided into two parts. The researcher pilot tested the questionnaire at a nearby school, aiming to achieve a Cronbach's alpha value greater than 0.700 to ensure high internal consistency. Scaling was set by establishing one-half of the value of 5 as the average cut-off point, with a uniform interval of 0.80. Before administering the instrument, it underwent validation by three experts, with revisions made based on their feedback. The first part of the instrument addressed the institutional leadership of school heads. This questionnaire consisted of four domains: learning environment stewardship, teacher professional growth, educational planning competence, and student discipline. The researcher modified the questionnaire by organizing all items under each dimension within the respective domain. Respondents answered these items using a 5-point Likert scale. The second part of the instrument focused on instructional engagement of teachers which was divided into four domains: cultivation of critical thinking, promotion of students' engagement, active classroom engagement, and integration of technology. The researcher organized the items by grouping each dimension under its respective domain. Respondents answered these items on a 5-point Likert scale. The third part of the instrument focused on the resource allocation proficiency of school heads. Responses were gathered using a 5-point Likert scale, allowing for precise measurement of agreement or disagreement with each item. This data was then analyzed using predefined mean ranges to effectively categorize and interpret the results.

the Dean of the Graduate School at The Rizal Memorial Colleges, Inc., Davao City. This endorsement served as a formal recognition and support of the research project, validating its

Range of Mean and Descriptive Level on Institutional Leadership of School Heads

Range of Mean	Descriptive Level	Interpretation
4.20 – 5.00	Very Extensive	The institutional leadership of school heads is always observed.
3.40 – 4.19	Extensive	The institutional leadership of school heads is oftentimes observed.
2.60 – 3.39	Moderately Extensive	The institutional leadership of school heads is sometimes observed.
1.80 – 2.59	Less Extensive	The institutional leadership of school heads is seldom observed.
1.00 – 1.79	Not Extensive	The institutional leadership of school heads is never observed.

Range of Mean and Descriptive Level on Teachers’ Instructional Commitment

Range of Mean	Descriptive Level	Interpretation
4.20 – 5.00	Very Extensive	Teachers’ instructional commitment is always manifested.
3.40 – 4.19	Extensive	Teachers’ instructional commitment is oftentimes manifested.
2.60 – 3.39	Moderately Extensive	Teachers’ instructional commitment is sometimes manifested.
1.80 – 2.59	Less Extensive	Teachers’ instructional commitment is seldom manifested.
1.00 – 1.79	Not Extensive	Teachers’ instructional commitment is never manifested.

academic merit and alignment with the institution’s research objectives. Subsequently, the researcher applied for ethical clearance from the Graduate School RMC-Research Ethics Committee (GSRMC-REC). The ethical clearance was crucial as it ensured that the study adhered to established ethical standards, particularly in terms of confidentiality, consent, and the overall welfare of the respondents. Once the endorsement and ethical clearance were secured, the researcher approached the Schools Division Superintendent in Davao de Oro to request permission to conduct the study within the schools

of Laak South District. This request included attaching copies of both the endorsement from the Dean and the ethical clearance certificate to demonstrate compliance with academic and ethical standards. Following approval from the superintendent, the researcher proceeded to contact the principals of the individual schools in Laak South District. During this phase, the researcher explained the study’s purpose, its potential benefits for the educational community, and the specific roles and expectations of the schools and their teachers, ensuring transparency and fostering cooperation.

2.6. *Data Analysis*—

Range of Mean and Descriptive Level on Resource Allocation Proficiency of School Heads

Range of Mean	Description	Interpretation
4.20 – 5.00	Very Extensive	The resource allocation proficiency of school heads is always demonstrated.
3.40 – 4.19	Extensive	The resource allocation proficiency of school heads is oftentimes demonstrated.
2.60 – 3.39	Moderately Extensive	The resource allocation proficiency of school heads is sometimes demonstrated.
1.80 – 2.59	Less Extensive	The resource allocation proficiency of school heads is seldom demonstrated.
1.00 – 1.79	Not Extensive	The resource allocation proficiency of school heads is never demonstrated.

The following were the statistical tools utilized by the researcher in processing the gathered data: Mean. this study, this referred to the average score derived from the institutional leadership, resource allocation proficiency of school heads, and teachers’ instructional engagement. It provided a central tendency measure that represented the overall perceptions and experiences of the teachers within the Laak South District schools. Pearson Product-Moment Correlation. In this study, it was used to assess the strength and direction of the linear relationship between variables such as institutional leadership, resource allocation proficiency of school heads, and teachers’ instructional engagement. It helped determine whether higher levels of institutional leadership and resource allocation proficiency of school heads were associated with higher levels of teachers’ instructional engagement, providing insights into how these factors were interconnected within the school setting. Model Fit Indices. Model fit indices in this research were used to evaluate how well the data fit the hypothesized measurement model in the path analysis. Indices such as Chi-square, RMSEA (Root Mean Square Error of Approximation), CFI (Comparative Fit Index), and TLI (Tucker-Lewis Index) were calculated to assess

the adequacy of the model structures in representing the relationships among institutional leadership, resource allocation proficiency of school heads, and teachers’ instructional engagement. Path Analysis. Path analysis through Structural Equation Modeling (SEM) in this context was a multivariate statistical analysis technique that allowed for the examination of complex causal relationships between variables involved in institutional leadership, resource allocation proficiency of school heads, and teachers’ instructional engagement. It involved estimating direct and indirect effects within the proposed model to understand how variables like resource allocation proficiency mediated the relationship between institutional leadership of school heads and teachers’ instructional engagement. Sobel z-Test. In this study, the Sobel z-Test was employed to determine the significance of the mediation effect of resource allocation proficiency on the relationship between institutional leadership of school heads and teachers’ instructional engagement. This test calculated the standard error of the indirect effect of the mediator, providing a z-score to assess whether the mediation was statistically significant, thus verifying the strength of the indirect paths within the SEM model.

3. Results and Discussion

This chapter presents the results generated from the data gathered. It is sequenced based on the objectives of the study as presented in the first chapter. Thus, it presents the extents of institutional leadership, resource allocation proficiency of school heads, and instructional engagement of teachers; and the mediating effect of resource allocation proficiency on the relationship between institutional leadership and instructional engagement of 293 elementary school teachers located in the Laak South District of Davao de Oro.

3.1. Institutional Leadership—Table 1 shows that institutional leadership of school heads in Laak South District, Davao de Oro yielded an overall mean of 3.40, interpreted as extensive, which indicates that school leadership practices are frequently observed across key governance domains. This suggests that school heads generally exhibit effective leadership in maintaining academic standards, supporting teacher development, fostering inclusive learning environments, and planning educational strategies. According to Devi and Fernandes (2019), strong institutional leadership is foundational to achieving sustained school improvement and driving academic success through visionary governance and collaborative management. The findings imply that leadership practices across the district are aligned with institutional goals, creating a structured and supportive educational setting.

Table 1. Summary on Institutional Leadership of School Heads in Laak South District, Davao de Oro

Indicators	Mean	Descriptive Equivalent
Learning Environment Stewardship	3.51	Extensive
Teacher Professional Growth	3.41	Extensive
Educational Planning Competence	3.47	Extensive
Student Discipline	3.22	Moderately Extensive
Overall	3.40	Extensive

Note. Very Extensive = Always observed; Extensive = Oftentimes observed; Moderately Extensive = Sometimes observed; Less Extensive = Seldom observed; Not Extensive = Never observed.

3.2. Instructional Engagement—Table 2 result shows that instructional engagement of teachers in Laak South District, Davao de Oro yielded an overall mean of 3.31, interpreted as moderately extensive, which indicates that instructional engagement practices are sometimes manifested across classrooms. This suggests that while teachers demonstrate a foundational awareness of instructional strategies such as critical thinking cultivation, student engagement, and classroom interactivity, these practices are not yet consistently or fully integrated into daily instruction. According to Shu (2022), consistent and intentional instructional engagement is a key factor in improving student achievement, making it essential for educators to adopt and maintain practices that support active and reflective learning. The findings imply a need for strengthened instructional leadership, targeted professional development, and ongoing classroom support to bridge the gap between theory and consistent application. As noted by Cacciamani et al. (2022), enhancing instructional engagement can help foster deeper learning and improved student outcomes across the district. Among the four indicators, Promotion

of Students' Engagement recorded the highest mean at 3.44, interpreted as extensive, indicating that teachers frequently employ strategies to involve students actively in the learning process. Conversely, Integration of Technology obtained the lowest mean at 3.18, interpreted as moderately extensive, revealing that digital tools are

only sometimes used as part of instruction. As noted by Fute et al. (2022), meaningful technology integration is contingent on teacher beliefs, training, and support systems. These findings highlight the importance of ongoing capacity building and resource provision to fully realize the benefits of technology enhanced instruction.

Table 2. Summary on Instructional Engagement of Teachers in Laak West District, Davao de Oro

Indicators	Mean	Descriptive Equivalent
Cultivation of Critical Thinking	3.32	Moderately Extensive
Promotion of Students' Engagement	3.44	Extensive
Active Classroom Engagement	3.28	Moderately Extensive
Integration of Technology	3.18	Moderately Extensive
Overall Mean	3.31	Moderately Extensive

Note. Very Extensive = Always manifested; Extensive = Oftentimes manifested; Moderately Extensive = Sometimes manifested; Less Extensive = Seldom manifested; Not Extensive = Never manifested.

3.3. Resource Allocation Proficiency— The extent of resource allocation proficiency of school heads in Laak South District, Davao de Oro yielded an overall mean of 3.25, interpreted as moderately extensive, indicating that resource management practices are sometimes demonstrated across schools. This result implies that while school heads recognize the significance of efficient and equitable resource distribution, actual implementation of such practices may vary in consistency and scope. As

emphasized by Devanadera and Ching (2023), effective school leadership entails strategic allocation of resources to support instructional priorities, enhance teacher performance, and address student needs. The moderately extensive rating suggests that although efforts are evident particularly in areas such as instructional materials and teacher development greater coordination and accountability mechanisms may be necessary to ensure more impactful and transparent use of school resources (Tapala et al., 2021).

The item means ranged from 3.09 to 3.37, reflecting variability in how specific resource allocation strategies are applied. The highest-rated statement, investing in professional development opportunities for all staff members, received a mean of 3.37, interpreted as moderately extensive, which suggests a growing recognition of the importance of enhancing teacher competencies through sustained learning opportunities. In contrast, the lowest-rated item, supporting extracurricular activities through ade-

quate resource allocation, obtained a mean of 3.09, also moderately extensive, highlighting that non-academic areas such as extracurriculars receive less prioritization. This aligns with the findings of Ongori (2021), who noted that schools often underinvest in extracurricular programs despite their role in promoting student engagement and holistic development. Addressing such imbalances by broadening the focus of resource distribution to include both academic and co-curricular needs will contribute to more eq-

Table 3. Summary on Resource Allocation Proficiency of School Heads in Laak South District, Davao de Oro

Statement	Mean	Descriptive Rating
Allocating sufficient resources for innovative teaching methods	3.21	Moderately Extensive
Ensuring equitable distribution of resources among different departments	3.19	Moderately Extensive
Prioritizing funding towards essential educational tools and materials	3.36	Moderately Extensive
Investing in professional development opportunities for all staff members	3.37	Moderately Extensive
Managing financial resources transparently and efficiently	3.36	Moderately Extensive
Supporting extracurricular activities through adequate resource allocation	3.09	Moderately Extensive
Addressing the technological needs of the classroom effectively	3.28	Moderately Extensive
Facilitating improvements in school infrastructure with available funds	3.15	Moderately Extensive
Overall Mean	3.25	Moderately Extensive

Note. Very Extensive = Always demonstrated; Extensive = Oftentimes demonstrated; Moderately Extensive = Sometimes demonstrated; Less Extensive = Seldom demonstrated; Not Extensive = Never demonstrated.

uitable and well-rounded school environments.

3.4. Relationship among Institutional Leadership, Resource Allocation Proficiency of School Heads, and Instructional Engagement of Teachers—The results on the analysis of the relationship among institutional leadership, resource allocation proficiency of school heads, and instructional engagement of teachers in Laak South District, Davao de Oro are presented. Bivariate correlation analysis using Pearson product moment correlation was utilized to assess the associations among the variables. The results revealed a strong and significant relationship between institutional leadership and instructional engagement ($r = 0.716$,

$p < 0.000$), indicating that the more effective and extensive the leadership practices of school heads, the more engaged teachers are in instructional delivery. This suggests that leadership that fosters supportive learning environments, professional development, and participatory governance directly influences teachers' motivation and commitment to effective teaching. As Skaalvik (2020) emphasize, instructional engagement thrives in schools where leadership builds professional capacity and supports pedagogical goals. Thus, improving institutional leadership enhances the quality and consistency of teaching practices within schools.

Likewise, a strong and significant correlation was found between institutional leadership and resource allocation proficiency of school

heads ($r = 0.637$, $p < 0.000$). This implies that the stronger the leadership exhibited by school heads, the more proficient they are in distribut-

Table 4. Relationship among Institutional Leadership, Resource Allocation Proficiency of School Heads, and Instructional Engagement of Teachers in Laak South District, Davao de Oro

Variables	Resource Allocation Proficiency	Instructional Engagement
Institutional Leadership	0.637**	0.716**
	0.000	0.000
Resource Allocation Proficiency	1.000	0.800**
		0.000

Note. **Significant at $p < 0.05$. Correlation strength: Perfect = 1.00; Strong = 0.70–0.99; Moderate = 0.30–0.69; Weak = 0.01–0.29; None = 0.00.

ing resources effectively, equitably, and transparently. Effective institutional leadership encompasses strategic planning, financial stewardship, and responsiveness to educational needs, as emphasized by Alvarez and Potane (2024). The data suggest that when school heads are actively engaged in institutional leadership, they are more capable of aligning resource decisions with instructional priorities and developmental goals. Practically, this means that strengthening school leadership not only guides vision and governance but also ensures that financial and material resources are optimally allocated to support teaching and learning. Finally, the study revealed a very strong and significant relationship between resource allocation proficiency of school heads and instructional engagement of teachers ($r = 0.800, p < 0.000$). This indicates that effective management of resources is closely tied to the degree to which teachers are able to engage students actively and meaningfully in instruction. When resources such as teaching materials, training opportunities, and technological tools are adequately provided, teachers are better equipped to deliver dynamic and learner-centered instruction. According to Nooruddin and Bhamani (2019), access to ap-

propriate resources is a key enabler of quality teaching and student achievement. The findings imply that resource proficiency acts as a bridge between leadership and classroom effectiveness—demonstrating that empowering school heads with both leadership and financial management skills leads to stronger instructional engagement among teachers.

3.5. *Mediation Analysis on Resource Allocation Proficiency of School Heads on Institutional Leadership and Teachers’ Instructional Engagement*—The Path Coefficients Table in the mediation analysis reveals statistically significant relationships among institutional leadership (Ins), resource allocation proficiency (Rsr), and instructional engagement (Eng) of teachers in Laak South District, Davao de Oro. Institutional leadership significantly predicts instructional engagement ($\beta = 0.376, p < .001$), indicating that school heads’ leadership practices directly influence the instructional efforts of teachers. Additionally, resource allocation proficiency strongly predicts instructional engagement ($\beta = 0.415, p < .001$), and institutional leadership significantly predicts resource allocation proficiency ($\beta = 0.965, p < .001$).

These findings suggest that school heads who exhibit effective leadership are not only directly improving teaching practices but are also

enhancing them indirectly by efficiently managing resources. As supported by Bellibaş et al. (2021), instructional leadership and resource

Table 5. The Mediating Effect of Resource Allocation Proficiency of School Heads on Institutional Leadership and Teachers’ Instructional Engagement in Laak South District, Davao de Oro

Path / Effect Type	Estimate	Std. Error	z-value	p-value
<i>Path Coefficients (Steps)</i>				
(Step 1) Ins → Eng	0.376**	0.044	8.510	<.001
(Step 2) Rsr → Eng	0.415**	0.029	14.241	<.001
(Step 3) Ins → Rsr	0.965**	0.068	14.148	<.001
<i>Step 4: Parameter Estimates</i>				
Indirect Effect: Ins → Rsr → Eng	0.401	0.040	10.037	<.001
Direct Effect: Ins → Eng	0.376	0.044	8.510	<.001
Total Effect: Ins → Eng	0.777	0.044	17.535	<.001

Note. **Significant at $p < 0.05$. Sobel z-test = 10.0765, $p = 0.000$. Ratio Index = 0.51608. Ins = Institutional Leadership; Eng = Instructional Engagement; Rsr = Resource Allocation Proficiency.

mobilization are key levers for improving teaching quality and student outcomes, emphasizing the strategic role of leadership in educational effectiveness. In terms of the Parameter Estimates, the direct effect of institutional leadership on instructional engagement remains significant at = 0.376 ($p < .001$), while the indirect effect through resource allocation proficiency is also strong and significant at = 0.401 ($p < .001$). The total effect of institutional leadership on instructional engagement is = 0.777, which indicates that resource allocation proficiency partially mediates the relationship between leadership and instructional engagement. This means that effective leadership alone contributes to instructional outcomes, but its influence is amplified when leaders also exhibit strong resource management capabilities. According to Copriady et al. (2021), resource allocation should be aligned with instructional priorities to produce meaningful learning gains. The Ratio Index of 0.51608 indicates that approximately 51.6% of the total effect of institutional leadership on instructional engagement is mediated by resource allocation proficiency, suggesting a substantial partial me-

diation. The Sobel z-Test value of 10.0765 ($p = 0.000$) provides strong statistical evidence that this mediating effect is not due to chance, confirming the robustness of the model. These results suggest that effective resource management is not just a complementary administrative function, but a crucial pathway through which leadership translates into enhanced instructional practices. As Meyer et al. (2022) pointed out, when teachers are supported with the right tools, training, and materials, their instructional performance improves significantly. The findings of this mediation analysis support the Transformational Leadership Theory of Burns (1978), which emphasizes that effective leaders inspire, support, and empower their followers to achieve higher performance. The results also align with the Resource-Based View (RBV) Theory of Barney (1991), which posits that organizational success depends on the effective management and deployment of valuable internal resources. Also, the results support Path-Goal Theory by House (1971), which asserts that leaders enhance employee performance by clarifying goals and providing necessary support.

4. Conclusions and Recommendations

This part of the paper presents the conclusion and recommendation of the researcher. The discussion is supported by the literature presented in the first chapters and the conclusion is in accordance with statements of the problem presented in this study.

4.1. Findings—The primary objective of this study was to evaluate how resource allocation proficiency mediates the relationship between institutional leadership and instructional engagement of teachers through structural equation modelling utilizing non-experimental quantitative design using descriptive-correlation technique. The researcher selected the 293 elementary school teachers located in the Laak South District of Davao de Oro as the respondents through simple random sampling method. The researcher made use of modified and enhanced adapted survey questionnaires which was pilot tested in a nearby school to ensure high reliability and internal consistency of the items in the instrument. The result of the study is summarized as follows: First, the extent of institutional leadership of school heads in Laak South District, Davao de Oro is generally rated as extensive, indicating that leadership practices are frequently observed across schools. Among the indicators, learning environment stewardship is most extensively demonstrated, showing strong attention to creating positive school climates. However, leadership practices related to student discipline are only moderately extensive, suggesting the need for greater consistency in behavior management. Second, the extent of instructional engagement of teachers in Laak South District is moderately extensive, indicating that engagement strategies are sometimes evident in classroom instruction. Promotion of students' engagement is the most emphasized, reflecting teachers' efforts to foster active participation. In contrast, the integration of technology is the least practiced, highlighting a gap in digital instructional competence. Third, the resource allocation proficiency of school heads in Laak South District within Davao de Oro is moderately extensive, suggesting that resource management practices are inconsistently demonstrated. Investments in professional development and procurement of essential teaching materials are among the most practiced areas. On the other hand, allocation for extracurricular activities is less frequently observed, revealing a tendency to prioritize academic over holistic development. Fourth, findings reveal a strong positive correlation between institutional leadership and both resource allocation proficiency and instructional engagement, implying that effective leadership enhances resource use and teaching performance. Additionally, a very strong relationship exists between resource allocation proficiency and instructional engagement, indicating that well-managed resources significantly boost instructional practices. These results affirm that leadership and resource use are interconnected drivers of classroom effectiveness. Lastly, the results of the mediation analysis show that institutional leadership significantly influences instructional engagement both directly and indirectly through resource allocation proficiency. The partial mediation effect suggests that resource allocation accounts for a substantial portion of leadership's total impact on instruction. These findings demonstrate that leadership is most effective when complemented by strategic and equitable resource distribution.

4.2. Conclusions—Based on the findings of this study, several conclusions were generated: Institutional leadership of school heads in Laak South District is generally extensive, particularly in fostering positive learning environments and effective planning, though lead-

ership in student discipline remains less consistent. These findings imply that reinforcing disciplinary governance, alongside strong planning and stewardship, can further enhance school leadership effectiveness. School heads must maintain holistic leadership that balances academic and behavioral domains to sustain educational quality. Instructional engagement of teachers is moderately extensive, with strong emphasis on promoting student engagement, but with limited integration of technology in teaching practices. This suggests that while teachers are committed to active and participatory learning, their digital instructional skills and resource access may require further development. Thus, targeted professional development and provision of digital tools are essential for optimizing instructional delivery and modern classroom practices. Moreover, the significant relationships among institutional leadership, resource allocation proficiency, and instructional engagement confirm that leadership effectiveness is amplified through strategic resource management. These results support the Transformational Leadership Theory of Bass (1985), which highlights the importance of inspirational and supportive leadership; the Path-Goal Theory of House (1971), which emphasizes providing direction and resources to achieve goals; and the Leader-Member Exchange Theory of Dansereau et al. (1975), which values high-quality leader-follower relationships. Therefore, school heads must exhibit not only strong leadership but also effective stewardship of resources to fully engage teachers and enhance instructional outcomes.

4.3. Recommendations—In light of the study's findings, the following recommendations are offered to inform policy, school leadership, teaching practice, and future research: Institutional Leadership of School Heads. The lowest mean is observed in the domain of student discipline, indicating that leadership practices in this area are only moderately extensive.

School heads should strengthen their role in promoting consistent and proactive disciplinary systems across classrooms. Regular training on restorative practices, positive behavior support, and inclusive discipline strategies should be provided to ensure a fair and supportive learning environment. Instructional Engagement of Teachers. The integration of technology received the lowest mean among the indicators. Schools must provide targeted professional development programs focusing on digital literacy, educational technology tools, and blended learning strategies. Furthermore, school heads should ensure that infrastructure and digital resources are accessible, and that teachers are supported in using them effectively in daily instruction. Resource Allocation Proficiency of School Heads. The lowest mean is found in the support for extracurricular activities, reflecting a limited focus on holistic student development. School leaders are encouraged to allocate designated funding for co-curricular and extracurricular programs that support students' social and emotional growth. Additionally, collaboration with community stakeholders can help expand activity offerings without compromising core academic resources. Relationship among Institutional Leadership, Resource Allocation, and Instructional Engagement. While all correlations are statistically significant, the relationship between institutional leadership and resource allocation proficiency is the weakest among the three. This suggests the need for improved training of school heads in financial planning, budgeting, and strategic allocation aligned with instructional goals. Strengthening school heads' competency in managing and deploying resources can maximize the impact of their leadership on teacher performance. Mediating Effect of Resource Allocation Proficiency. The partial mediation effect reveals that a considerable portion of leadership's influence on instructional engagement is channeled through resource allocation. To enhance this pathway,

school heads should institutionalize evidence-based resource planning that prioritizes instructional needs. The findings of the investigation can help school heads identify areas of improvement in their leadership styles and resource management practices. It equips them with data-driven strategies to enhance their proficiency in allocating resources to optimize teacher engagement and student outcomes. Moreover, school heads can gain a deeper understanding of how their leadership directly impacts instructional quality, allowing them to implement targeted interventions to foster a more supportive teaching environment. This investigation can provide evidence-based insights into the effectiveness of leadership strategies and resource allocation practices in enhancing instructional engagement. By understanding the critical factors influ-

encing teacher performance, DepEd can design policies that strengthen leadership training and allocate resources more effectively to schools. Additionally, the study can serve as a basis for improving school management frameworks, ensuring alignment with educational goals and national standards.

The study provides a foundation for future research on educational leadership, resource management, and teacher engagement. It offers a comprehensive framework for exploring similar dynamics in other contexts or extending the analysis to include additional variables such as student performance or community involvement. Future researchers can build on these findings to further understand the complexities of educational leadership and its far-reaching impacts.

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